

K-Sense: A Non-Invasive eBPF Framework for QoS Inference

Abdullah Muslim, Ali Beiti Aydenlou, and Stephan Recker

Department of Computer Science

University of Applied Sciences and Arts

Dortmund, Germany

{abdullah.muslim,ali.beitiaydenlou,stephan.recker}@fh-dortmund.de

Abstract—Edge nodes host latency-sensitive applications on fixed and resource-limited hardware. Under moderate load increases, contention for shared CPU, network, and I/O resources introduces kernel-level delays that result in tail-latency degradation. In practice, many edge workloads are black-box services, making application-level instrumentation impractical. Existing resource metrics such as CPU utilization and Linux Pressure Stall Information (PSI) often fail to explain latency behavior, especially when they saturate.

We present *K-Sense*, a non-invasive eBPF-based framework that infers QoS degradation from kernel behavior. *K-Sense* collects a small set of kernel-level delay metrics and represents the system state as a point in a multi-dimensional feature space. It then computes a covariance-aware *friction* signal using the Mahalanobis distance to quantify deviation from a calibrated normal operating region.

We evaluate *K-Sense* on a Kubernetes testbed using real microservice workloads from DeathStarBench and a sentiment-analysis application. Results show that friction tracks application P99 latency under changing load and continues to reflect latency variations when CPU utilization and PSI saturate. These signals provide a practical basis for higher-level actions such as admission control, scheduling, and workload migration without requiring application modification.

Index Terms—eBPF, observability, kernel tracing, QoS inference, edge computing, Mahalanobis distance

I. INTRODUCTION

Edge computing brings computation closer to end users in order to meet the latency requirements of interactive and real-time applications [1]. As a result, latency-sensitive services such as online inference, content personalization, and interactive microservices are increasingly deployed on edge nodes.

Despite these advantages, maintaining consistent performance at the edge is challenging. In centralized cloud data centers, performance degradation is commonly mitigated through horizontal scaling. Edge environments, however, face stricter limitations. Edge nodes are typically hosted on spatially constrained platforms, such as gateways, base stations, or on-premise micro-data centers, where computational resources are static [2]. Due to these physical and resource boundaries, horizontal scaling is often impractical, leaving vertical scaling within fixed capacity limits as the primary strategy. Consequently, even moderate increases in workload intensity can lead to contention for shared resources and measurable performance degradation.

From an operational perspective, edge and cloud platforms often host applications that cannot be modified or fully observed, such as proprietary binaries or workloads owned by independent stakeholders [3]. In such settings, application-level tracing typically requires intrusive instrumentation or code changes, which are difficult to maintain and often not permitted by application owners in production environments [4]. As a result, relying on direct application-level performance metrics is often impractical at runtime, and operators must instead infer user-perceived Quality of Service (QoS) from non-intrusive, system-level signals [5].

From the user’s perspective, QoS is primarily determined by response time, which we refer to as *latency*. While edge computing reduces network delay, processing delays within the node remain a dominant source of latency under load. These delays arise from contention in shared compute resources such as CPU time, interrupt handling, and I/O execution when multiple workloads execute concurrently. In the absence of direct visibility into application behavior, understanding and detecting QoS degradation therefore requires monitoring the system layers where these shared resources are managed.

Existing monitoring approaches are poorly suited to this setting. High-level resource metrics, such as CPU or memory utilization, do not reliably capture user-perceived latency. A system may appear lightly loaded while requests still experience high response times due to factors such as scheduling delays or blocking I/O [5]. Techniques that directly measure latency, including application-level tracing or active probing, can offer more accurate insight, but they introduce additional overhead and typically depend on access to application internals. These requirements make such techniques unsuitable for many production edge environments, where applications are resource-constrained and treated as black boxes.

Recent advances in Extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) technology enable practical and low-overhead monitoring directly at the kernel level [6]. Using eBPF, system operators can observe fine-grained kernel events related to scheduling, I/O, and execution without requiring any application modification. Prior work has demonstrated that such kernel-level signals exhibit strong correlation with application latency and user-perceived performance [7], [8]. However, these signals are often noisy and high-dimensional [9], which makes it challenging to derive reliable, high-level QoS indicators from raw

kernel measurements alone.

In this paper, we present *K-Sense*, a non-invasive, application-agnostic framework for inferring QoS degradation from kernel behavior. To address the challenge of noisy and high-dimensional kernel metrics, *K-Sense* adopts a distance-based metric learning approach to integrate multiple kernel signals into a single indicator of system stress [10]. *K-Sense* models the system state as a point in a multi-dimensional space defined by latency-correlated kernel metrics. During normal operation, the system occupies a stable region of this space. As resource contention increases, the system state moves away from this region. We quantify this deviation using the Mahalanobis distance [11], which normalizes metrics with different value ranges and captures the correlation between them, resulting in a single *friction* signal that summarizes kernel-level contention.

By aggregating kernel-level behavior into a unified indicator, *K-Sense* avoids manual threshold tuning and does not rely on application instrumentation. While it does not aim to identify the root cause of contention, the resulting kernel-level *friction* signal provides a reliable basis for higher-level decisions such as admission control, workload migration, or adaptive resource management.

A. Contributions

The main contributions of this work are:

- **Kernel-Latency Analysis:** We identify kernel tracepoints whose behavior consistently correlates with application tail latency in multi-tenant environments.
- **Friction Metric:** We introduce a covariance-aware kernel-level friction metric based on the Mahalanobis distance that captures QoS degradation without application knowledge or manual thresholds.
- **Evaluation with Real Applications:** We evaluate *K-Sense* using real containerized workloads from the Death-StarBench suite¹ and demonstrate its ability to track latency degradation under dynamic load.

II. METHODOLOGY AND STRUCTURE

Our methodology proceeds in two phases. First, we revisit kernel events reported in prior eBPF-based studies and analyze how they correlate with application tail latency in a multi-tenant, microservice-based environment. Based on this analysis, we select a small set of representative CPU, network, and I/O metrics that consistently correlate with tail-latency increases across workloads. Second, we combine these metrics into a unified system friction signal using the Mahalanobis distance and evaluate the approach in an edge setting using real-world workloads.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section III discusses related work, Section IV presents the identification of latency-correlated kernel events, Section V describes the design of *K-Sense*, Section VI details the experimental setup and evaluation, and Section VII discusses design considerations and practical implications of *K-Sense*.

III. RELATED WORK

Although eBPF was originally designed for networking and packet processing, it has since evolved into a widely used tool for system observability. Prior work in this area typically falls into two categories: application-aware tracing and kernel-level metric analysis.

Application-Aware Tracing. Most observability systems measure request latency by analyzing application-layer (L7) traffic. Kernel-level tracing systems such as *Nahida* [12] and *DeepFlow* [13] reconstruct request paths by inspecting packet payloads and socket interactions within the kernel. However, this approach breaks down when traffic is encrypted (e.g., HTTPS or mTLS), as the kernel cannot access plaintext payloads to recover request context.

To address this limitation, systems such as *Pixie* [14] and service meshes like *Istio* [15] rely on sidecar proxies or user-space probes (uprobes) to capture requests before encryption. While effective, these techniques are not application-agnostic: they require protocol-specific parsers and instrumentation. Applications that use custom or unsupported protocols are therefore difficult to monitor. Moreover, sidecars and deep packet inspection introduce non-trivial CPU overhead, which is particularly problematic for resource-constrained edge environments [16].

Kernel Signals and Latency. Kernel-level approaches avoid application-layer complexity by inferring performance from system-level signals. eBPF-based tools such as *MiSeR-Trace* [17] and *bpffmon* [8] capture fine-grained kernel events with low overhead. However, interpreting these raw signals remains challenging. Rezvani *et al.* [5] show that although eBPF provides robust kernel visibility, it lacks explicit request boundaries, making accurate per-request latency reconstruction impractical for complex, multi-threaded applications.

This limitation motivates the need for higher-level indicators that aggregate kernel behavior rather than attempting fine-grained request tracing. *K-Sense* follows this direction by adopting an application-agnostic design in which applications are treated as black boxes. It monitors kernel behaviors such as scheduling delay, interrupt handling, and I/O blocking to capture how workloads interact with shared system resources in multi-tenant environments. These signals are combined using distance metric learning to produce a single *friction* metric, enabling QoS inference without sidecars, protocol parsers, or application instrumentation.

IV. IDENTIFYING LATENCY-CORRELATED KERNEL EVENTS

Before developing *K-Sense*, we identified which kernel signals strongly correlate with application latency. We revisited previous eBPF-based studies on system calls and tracepoints [5], [7] to verify if their findings apply in a multi-tenant, microservices-based environment.

A. eBPF-Based Data Collection

We use eBPF to run monitoring code inside the Linux kernel. eBPF programs run in a restricted virtual machine

¹<https://github.com/delimitrou/DeathStarBench>

TABLE I: Instrumented System Calls and Kernel Tracepoints

Event	Description
System Calls	
read, write	Measures read and write latency for disk and network I/O.
sendto, recvfrom, sendmsg, recvmsg	Captures application-level network send and receive latency.
poll, ppoll, epoll_wait, epoll_pwait, select, pselect6, futex	Observes waiting behavior caused by I/O readiness or synchronization events.
connect, accept, accept4	Tracks TCP connection setup and server-side accept latency.
fsync, fdatasync	Captures latency associated with flushing data to persistent storage.
nanosleep	Monitors voluntary sleep behavior.
stat, fstat	Measures latency of file metadata operations.
Kernel Tracepoints	
sched_switch, sched_wakeup, sched_wakeup_new	Measures CPU scheduling latency, run queue length (runqlen), and logic for tracking uninterruptible sleep (dstate).
softirq_entry, softirq_exit	Tracks time spent handling software interrupts, primarily for network processing.
block_rq_issue, block_rq_complete, block_rq_merge	Measures block I/O latency, queue depth (io_qdepth), and request merging.

(VM) inside the kernel. Before our program is allowed to run, the kernel verifier checks the code to make sure it cannot access invalid memory or freeze the node. The process works in three steps:

- 1) **Attach:** We connect our eBPF programs to specific kernel tracepoints.
- 2) **Aggregate:** On each event, the program updates shared eBPF maps, aggregating metrics in-kernel to minimize user-kernel transfer overhead.
- 3) **Read:** Our user-space application reads the final values from the maps once per second (1 s intervals).

We traced a total of 29 events, comprising 21 system calls and 8 kernel tracepoints. These are listed in Table I.

B. Benchmark Applications

To emulate a multi-tenant setting, we deploy two microservice-based applications and one AI inference application on a node running Linux kernel 6.8.0 with eBPF support.

- **Social Network:** A microservice-based application from the DeathStarBench suite that simulates a social networking service.
- **Hotel Reservation:** A microservice-based application from DeathStarBench that simulates hotel search and booking functionality.
- **Sentiment Analysis:** A custom Python-based application that performs sentiment analysis on text data using a pre-trained model².

C. Correlation Analysis

To identify kernel events correlated with application latency, we ran all three applications concurrently on a single node. We collected the kernel metrics listed in Table I and measured application P99 latency, aggregating both at 1 s intervals.

We then calculated the Spearman correlation between each kernel metric and application latency. Spearman’s rank correlation has been widely applied in performance analysis to

Fig. 1: Spearman correlation between kernel metrics and application latency.

identify monotonic relationships between system metrics and service-level behavior [18].

Fig. 1 presents the 10 kernel events with the highest correlation across the workloads. The results show that CPU scheduling latency, I/O blocking time (D-State), and network interrupt handling consistently correlate well with application latency. This indicates that kernel-level contention and blocking are useful indicators for identifying the sources of latency degradation in multi-tenant environments.

Furthermore, based on the Spearman correlation values in Fig. 1, we selected the single metric with the maximum correlation coefficient from each major kernel subsystem (CPU, network, and I/O) to ensure we capture bottlenecks across all subsystems. Specifically, we chose CPU scheduling latency, SoftIRQ processing time, and D-state I/O latency.

These metrics represent different sources of latency inside the Linux kernel:

²<https://github.com/BhanuPDas/CustomerFeedback>

Fig. 2: Spearman correlation between normalized kernel metrics (columns) and normalized P99 latency (rows); each subplot reports the correlation coefficient (ρ), sample size (n), and significance (p -value).

a) *Scheduler Latency*: Scheduler latency is the time runnable tasks wait before getting CPU time. It reflects CPU contention when multiple tasks compete to run. High scheduler latency means ready tasks are delayed, increasing application latency.

b) *SoftIRQ processing time*: SoftIRQ processing time is the CPU time spent handling software interrupts, such as network packet processing. High SoftIRQ activity increases kernel overhead, delays normal task execution, and raises application latency.

c) *D-State Latency*: D-state latency is the time tasks spend in uninterruptible sleep waiting for disk or network I/O. High D-state latency indicates blocking I/O that delays request processing even when CPU is available.

To analyze how changes in these three specific kernel delays translate to application performance, Fig. 2 shows the relationship between the selected kernel metrics and application P99 latency. Rows correspond to kernel metrics and columns to applications; all values are min–max normalized. Each subplot reports the Spearman correlation coefficient (ρ), the number of samples (n), and the associated p -value.

Across all applications, low kernel latency aligns with low P99 latency, while higher kernel latency corresponds to higher tail latency. This results in strong monotonic correlations, with ρ values ranging from 0.67 to 0.97 ($p < 0.001$). Although the spread differs across kernel components (CPU scheduling, network SoftIRQ processing, and I/O blocking), the overall trend remains consistent, indicating that increases in kernel

delay reliably lead to higher application tail latency.

Several CPU, network, and I/O kernel metrics correlate strongly with application P99 latency (Fig. 1), but these correlations often arise from interactions among kernel subsystems. For example, heavy network processing can consume CPU time and delay application scheduling, causing multiple metrics to increase even when the root cause is network-related [19]. As a result, a single metric can be misleading and may not reflect the true source or severity of performance problems.

This motivates an approach that analyzes kernel metrics together rather than individually. During normal operation, these metrics vary in a correlated manner. By learning this normal relationship, the system can detect when their behavior deviates, indicating abnormal execution stress across CPU, network, and I/O resources. In the next section, we present a method that follows this principle to construct a unified kernel-level stress signal.

V. K-SENSE DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

This section describes the design of *K-Sense* and how it derives kernel-level signals for QoS inference. *K-Sense* aggregates a small set of latency-correlated kernel metrics into a multi-dimensional system state and uses a covariance-aware distance to compute a unified *friction* metric. An additional *energy* signal captures short-term instability by measuring how rapidly friction changes over time.

A. Kernel Metrics

K-Sense uses three kernel metrics:

- **CPU scheduling latency** (x_{sched}): P99 scheduling delay per 1 s interval,
- **SoftIRQ processing time** (x_{softirq}): total network SoftIRQ processing time per 1 s interval, and
- **D-state I/O latency** (x_{dstate}): total time spent in uninterruptible I/O sleep per 1 s interval.

B. System State Representation

1) *Feature Vector*: At each time interval t , *K-Sense* represents the node state as a feature vector:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \begin{bmatrix} \text{SchedLat}_{p99}(t) \\ \text{SoftIRQ}_{\text{total}}(t) \\ \text{DState}_{\text{total}}(t) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

This vector captures kernel-level delay across CPU, network, and I/O subsystems in a compact, multi-dimensional form.

C. Friction: Deviation from Normal Operation

1) *Mahalanobis Distance*: *K-Sense* quantifies how far the current system state deviates from normal behavior using the Mahalanobis distance. We model normal behavior by estimating a baseline mean vector $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ from samples collected under stable operation. The resulting *friction* metric F_t is:

$$F_t = \sqrt{(\mathbf{x}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu})^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1} (\mathbf{x}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu})}. \quad (2)$$

This formulation has two practical benefits:

- **Range normalization:** kernel metrics have different numerical ranges; the covariance term normalizes these differences so that no single metric dominates.
- **Correlation awareness:** kernel subsystems often vary together. Mahalanobis distance accounts for these dependencies and reduces false alarms compared to treating metrics as independent.

D. Friction Direction

The Mahalanobis distance is always non-negative; therefore, F_t reflects only the magnitude of deviation from the reference system behavior and not its direction. Each system state corresponds to a point in the kernel-metric space, where deviation may occur along any direction relative to the baseline. When the reference behavior is learned under higher load, the baseline mean can be large. As a result, during production operation under lower load, the system may still exhibit a non-zero friction value despite operating normally.

To distinguish such cases from true pressure increases, we add a direction (Dir.) variable that indicates whether friction is above or below the calibrated baseline.

E. Energy: Temporal Instability of Friction

Friction quantifies deviation from normal operation but does not capture how this deviation evolves over time. To address this, *K-Sense* introduces an additional signal, termed *energy*, which reflects short-term instability in friction.

At each second, we compute the absolute change between consecutive friction values:

$$\Delta F_t = |F_t - F_{t-1}|. \quad (3)$$

Energy is defined as the average of these changes over a sliding window:

$$E_t = \frac{1}{W_t - 1} \sum_{i=t-W_t+2}^t \Delta F_i. \quad (4)$$

High energy values indicate rapid changes in friction, while low values indicate stable behavior. The window size W_t is adjusted dynamically based on recent friction variability, allowing energy to remain responsive during stable periods while suppressing noise during rapid fluctuations. Energy does not modify the friction signal and is computed only as an additional instability indicator.

F. Computational Complexity

Computing F_t requires matrix-vector operations with time complexity $O(d^2)$, where d is the number of kernel metrics. Since *K-Sense* uses only three metrics ($d = 3$), the computational overhead is negligible.

G. Operational Workflow of *K-Sense*

Algorithm 1 summarizes the complete online workflow of *K-Sense*.

The system operates in two phases: a *calibration phase*, where normal behavior is learned, and a *production phase*, where friction and energy are computed continuously from kernel measurements.

Algorithm 1 *K-Sense* Algorithm: Calibration and Production

Require: Baseline size N , window bounds $[W_{\min}, W_{\max}]$
Ensure: Friction F_t , Direction Dir_t , Energy E_t

- 1: **Calibration Phase:**
- 2: Collect N feature vectors \mathbf{x}_t
- 3: Estimate mean $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and covariance $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$
- 4: Compute baseline friction mean \bar{F}_{cal}
- 5: **Production Phase:**
- 6: **for** each time step t **do**
- 7: Measure current state \mathbf{x}_t
- 8: $F_t \leftarrow \sqrt{(\mathbf{x}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu})^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1} (\mathbf{x}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu})}$
- 9: $\text{Dir}_t \leftarrow \text{sign}(F_t - \bar{F}_{\text{cal}})$
- 10: Update adaptive window size W_t
- 11: $E_t \leftarrow \frac{1}{W_t - 1} \sum_{k=0}^{W_t - 2} |F_{t-k} - F_{t-k-1}|$
- 12: **return** (F_t, Dir_t, E_t)

H. System Architecture

Fig. 3 illustrates the system architecture of *K-Sense*. *K-Sense* is deployed as a privileged Kubernetes *DaemonSet*, enabling kernel-level monitoring through eBPF.

Application microservices run as standard Kubernetes pods in user space and generate CPU, network, and I/O activity. The *K-Sense* framework loads eBPF programs into the Linux kernel using `libbpf` and attaches them to selected kernel hook points, including CPU scheduling latency, network SoftIRQ processing, and uninterruptible I/O sleep.

The eBPF programs aggregate latency statistics in kernel-resident maps. These aggregated values are read once per second by *K-Sense* in user space and used to compute the friction and energy signals.

Fig. 3: Architecture of *K-Sense*. eBPF-based kernel monitoring for system friction estimation.

TABLE II: System Specifications

Component	Specification
Environment	KVM-based virtual machine
OS	Ubuntu 22.04.5 LTS
Kernel	Linux 6.8.0-90-generic
CPU	AMD EPYC 7643 (virtualized)
CPU Cores (vCPU)	16
CPU Frequency	2.0 GHz
Caches (L1/L2/L3)	1 MB / 8 MB / 256 MB
Memory	64 GB ECC RAM
Storage	200 GB virtual disk

Application clients run outside the monitored cluster to avoid interference with kernel-level measurements.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND RESULTS

We evaluate *K-Sense* on a single-node Kubernetes cluster hosted on a KVM-based VM and running multiple latency-sensitive microservices. Table II summarizes the hardware and software configuration. The objective of our experiments is to assess whether the proposed kernel-level *friction* metric correlates with application-level latency degradation.

We use the benchmark applications described in Section IV-B.

Each experiment runs for one hour. The first ten minutes (min) are reserved for calibrating *K-Sense*, during which normal operating behavior is learned by estimating the mean and covariance of the selected kernel metrics under stable conditions.

A. Calibration Phase

During calibration, we run two of the three applications: *Sentiment Analysis* and *Hotel Reservation*. The third application, *Social Network*, is not used in this phase. Calibration is only used to learn the normal behavior and covariance of latency-correlated kernel metrics and does not depend on application-specific logic.

We apply a step workload in which the request rate increases by 5 RPS every minute for 10 min. This controlled ramp-up allows *K-Sense* to observe how kernel metrics vary and covary under stable operation. We collect RPS, request success rate, and tail latency P99 at 1 s intervals.

To stay within the stable operating region, the offered load is reduced whenever latency exceeds $1.5\times$ the median latency over the previous 30 s. This factor is chosen for simplicity.

B. Production Phase

In the production phase, we include the *Social Network* application, which was not used during calibration, to evaluate whether the learned kernel baseline generalizes to a different workload.

To ensure accurate latency measurements, we separate latency observation from load generation. This avoids measurement bias, where a heavily loaded traffic generator may stall under congestion and fail to capture true latency spikes. The production setup therefore consists of two independent components:

1) *Latency Prober*: A lightweight client continuously sends a low, fixed-rate stream of requests (10 RPS) to each application. The client operates solely as an observer and records P99 latency at 1 s intervals. This provides a stable "ground truth" measurement without adding significant load to the system.

2) *Traffic Generator*: To emulate realistic cloud usage patterns, we use `wrk2`, a high-performance HTTP load generator, to drive traffic to the DSB applications. In addition, we deploy five instances of the Sentiment Analysis application. To introduce variability in system load, we randomly select between two and four instances to run concurrently every 10 min. Each selected instance runs for a random duration between 5 and 15 min. This setup creates time-varying resource pressure and reflects the behavior of a shared production cluster with dynamically changing workloads.

We evaluate *K-Sense* by comparing its friction signal (F_i) with CPU utilization and Linux Pressure Stall Information (PSI), a kernel metric that reports the fraction of time tasks are stalled due to resource contention [20]. All metrics, including PSI, are collected at 1 s intervals. The comparison focuses on how well each signal reflects application P99 latency degradation, particularly during high-latency periods.

Furthermore, we plot friction and energy on a logarithmic scale because their values change over a wide range as the system moves from normal operation to overload. The log scale makes it easier to see relative changes and to compare their patterns with CPU utilization and PSI.

C. Results

1) Comparison of Friction, PSI, and CPU Metrics:

a) *Friction, Energy, and Latency Dynamics*: Fig. 4a shows that the proposed friction signal follows application tail latency under changing load conditions. When friction increases, application P99 latency also rises, indicating that kernel-level latency plays an important role in performance degradation.

PSI shows a similar trend, as it also captures delays related to CPU contention. In contrast, CPU utilization becomes less informative once it reaches 100%, since it cannot reflect further increases in system stress. The energy signal captures short-term fluctuations in friction, revealing periods of unstable behavior. Furthermore, since calibration is performed under a controlled moderate load, the learned baseline has a higher mean. In the production phase, before the workload is deployed, the probe load remains below this baseline; as a result, the Mahalanobis distance stays lower than the calibrated mean, producing a negative friction direction that indicates operation below the calibrated load.

b) *Correlation with Application Latency*: Fig. 5 further shows that both friction and PSI have strong Spearman correlations with application P99 latency across all workloads. This suggests that kernel-level delay signals provide more useful QoS indicators than CPU utilization, especially in environments where moderate increases in latency are acceptable.

c) *State Space Visualization*: Fig. 6 illustrates how the Mahalanobis distance is used to measure deviation from

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4: Time-series comparison of kernel-level signals and application latency. (a) Unconstrained workloads: friction and energy follow application P99 latency under increasing load, while CPU utilization saturates. (b) CPU-limited workload: PSI reflects node-level pressure but loses alignment with application P99 latency, whereas friction continues to track latency variations.

Fig. 5: Correlation between system metrics and tail latency. P99 latency versus friction (top) and PSI (bottom) across three workloads (log scale), with Spearman’s ρ , n , and p -values.

normal system behavior. Friction is computed from three kernel metrics, forming a three-dimensional system state. For clarity, we visualize this space using pairwise two-dimensional projections.

Fig. 6: Pairwise projections of the kernel-metric state space showing calibration data, confidence regions, and friction magnitude.

The ellipses represent confidence regions derived from the chi-square (χ^2) distribution, where the degrees of freedom correspond to the number of metrics. System states within the normal operating region correspond to low friction, while states outside this region indicate significant deviation from the learned baseline and increasing friction. The shape of the confidence regions also shows that the kernel metrics in the feature vector are correlated rather than independent.

2) *Node-Level vs. Application-Level Visibility*: Fig. 4b shows a case where node-level metrics lose visibility into application-level latency behavior.

The calibration and probing setup remain unchanged. In the production phase, the sentiment-analysis pod is CPU-pinned,

unlike the previous unconstrained setup. As a result, its latency behavior is dominated by the CPU constraint, while variations in the other sentiment workload increase contention on the remaining CPU cores and primarily affect the other two applications. PSI measures stall time aggregated at the node level. When any pod on the node is CPU throttled, PSI increases for the entire node. While this correctly indicates system-wide pressure, it does not reflect the P99 latency behavior of the target application. After calibration, PSI increases more than CPU utilization, signaling pressure without high overall CPU usage.

Once PSI and CPU utilization reach 100%, both metrics saturate and lose sensitivity. In contrast, friction continues to track variations in application tail latency under the same conditions.

VII. DISCUSSION

K-Sense relies on a reference baseline learned during a calibration phase. This process is similar to training in machine learning systems, where correct behavior depends on how well the training data represents normal operation.

If calibration is performed under much higher load than usual, the learned baseline can shift. As a result, the friction magnitude F_t in production may be higher even when the system is operating normally. The direction indicator helps distinguish whether friction is above or below the baseline, but accurate and representative calibration remains important for reliable interpretation. To support further research and development, we open source K-Sense.³

CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

In this paper, we presented *K-Sense*, a non-invasive eBPF-based framework for inferring Quality of Service (QoS) degradation from kernel-level behavior. By combining latency-correlated kernel metrics into a single covariance-aware friction signal, K-Sense captures *friction* without requiring application instrumentation or manual thresholds. Our evaluation with real-world microservice workloads shows that friction closely tracks application tail latency and continues to reflect latency variations even when traditional metrics such as CPU utilization and PSI saturate.

K-Sense supports higher-level control decisions rather than root-cause diagnosis. Its friction and energy signals can guide admission control, scheduling, and workload migration decisions in resource-constrained edge environments where applications are treated as black boxes.

In future work, we plan to design an admission control mechanism for resource-constrained edge nodes that uses *K-Sense* to provide friction as an application-level QoS input derived from kernel behavior. A fuzzy controller will combine this signal with available resource metrics to support admission decisions for black-box workloads. We also plan to evaluate this approach in a multi-node cluster setting. In addition, we will further study calibration strategies to better define the

normal operating region under moderate load. Finally, we aim to extend *K-Sense* to support GPU-based workloads and hybrid CPU-GPU environments.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Satyanarayanan, "The emergence of edge computing," *Computer*, vol. 50, no. 1, pp. 30–39, 2017, doi: 10.1109/MC.2017.9.
- [2] F. Golpayegani, N. Chen, N. Afraz, E. Gyamfi, A. Malekjarfarian, D. Schäfer, and C. Krupitzer, "Adaptation in edge computing: A review on design principles and research challenges," *ACM Trans. Auton. Adapt. Syst.*, vol. 19, no. 3, Art. no. 19, 2024.
- [3] M. Usman, S. Ferlin, A. Brunstrom, and J. Taheri, "A survey on observability of distributed edge and container-based microservices," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 86904–86919, 2022.
- [4] S. Ashok, V. Harsh, B. Godfrey, R. Mittal, S. Parthasarathy, and L. Shwartz, "TraceWeaver: Distributed request tracing for microservices without application modification," in *Proc. ACM SIGCOMM*, 2024, pp. 828–842.
- [5] M. Rezvani, A. Jahanshahi, and D. Wong, "Characterizing in-kernel observability of latency-sensitive request-level metrics with eBPF," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Perform. Anal. Syst. Softw. (ISPASS)*, 2024, pp. 15–27, doi: 10.1109/ISPASS61541.2024.00010.
- [6] eBPF Foundation, "What is eBPF?," *eBPF.io*. [Online]. Available: <https://ebpf.io/what-is-ebpf/>.
- [7] T. Takagaki and K. Mizutani, "Deep analysis of containerized web server performance using eBPF-captured data," *IEEJ Trans. Electr. Electron. Eng.*, vol. 20, no. 11, pp. 1826–1828, 2025, doi: 10.1002/tee.70070.
- [8] C. Liu, Z. Cai, B. Wang, Z. Tang, and J. Liu, "A protocol-independent container network observability analysis system based on eBPF," in *Proc. IEEE 26th Int. Conf. Parallel Distrib. Syst. (ICPADS)*, 2020, pp. 697–702, doi: 10.1109/ICPADS51040.2020.00099.
- [9] B. Pijnacker, B. Setz, and V. Andrikopoulos, "Container-level energy observability in Kubernetes clusters," arXiv:2504.10702, 2025.
- [10] E. P. Xing, M. I. Jordan, S. J. Russell, and A. Y. Ng, "Distance metric learning with application to clustering with side-information," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 15. MIT Press, 2003.
- [11] P. C. Mahalanobis, "On the generalized distance in statistics," *Proc. Natl. Inst. Sci. India*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 49–55, 1936.
- [12] W. Yang, P. Chen, K. Liu, and H. Zhang, "Nahida: In-band distributed tracing with eBPF," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2311.09032*, 2023.
- [13] J. Shen, H. Zhang, Y. Xiang, X. Shi, X. Li, Y. Shen, Z. Zhang, Y. Wu, X. Yin, J. Wang, M. Xu, Y. Li, J. Yin, J. Song, Z. Li, and R. Nie, "Network-centric distributed tracing with DeepFlow: Troubleshooting your microservices in zero code," in *Proceedings of the ACM SIGCOMM 2023 Conference*, pp. 420–437, 2023.
- [14] Pixie Labs, "Pixie: Open-source Kubernetes observability using eBPF," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://px.dev/>.
- [15] Istio Authors, "Istio: An open platform to connect, manage, and secure microservices," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://istio.io/>.
- [16] X. Zhu, G. She, B. Xue, Y. Zhang, Y. Zhang, X. K. Zou, X. Duan, P. He, A. Krishnamurthy, M. Lentz, D. Zhuo, and R. Mahajan, "Dissecting overheads of service mesh sidecars," in *Proc. ACM Symp. Cloud Comput. (SoCC)*, 2023, pp. 142–157, doi: 10.1145/3620678.3624652.
- [17] T. V. Thirivikraman, V. R. Dixit, N. R. S., V. K. Gowda, S. K. Vasudevan, and S. Kalambur, "MiSeRTrace: Kernel-level request tracing for microservice visibility," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2203.14076*, 2022.
- [18] Z. Zhu, C. Lee, X. Tang, and P. He, "HeMiRCA: Fine-grained root cause analysis for microservices with heterogeneous data sources," *ACM Trans. Softw. Eng. Methodol.*, vol. 33, no. 8, Art. no. 200, 2024.
- [19] J. Khalid, E. Rozner, W. Felter, C. Xu, K. Rajamani, A. Ferreira, and A. Akella, "Iron: Isolating network-based CPU in container environments," in *Proc. 15th USENIX Symp. Netw. Syst. Des. Implement. (NSDI)*, 2018, pp. 313–328.
- [20] Facebook, "Pressure Stall Information," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://facebookmicrosites.github.io/psi/docs/overview>.

³<https://github.com/abmuslim/K-sense>